

Image not found or type unknown

Anniehs, Arnaldo Oscar (1915–1993)

THE BRAZILIAN WHITE CENTER – UNASP

The Brazilian White Center – UNASP is a team of teachers and students at the Brazilian Ellen G. White Research Center – UNASP at the Brazilian Adventist University, Campus Engenheiro, Coelho, SP. The team was supervised by Drs. Adolfo Semo Suárez, Renato Stencel, and Carlos Flávio Teixeira. Bruno Sales Gomes Ferreira provided technical support. The following names are of team members: Adriane Ferrari Silva, Álan Gracioto Alexandre, Allen Jair Urcia Santa Cruz, Camila Chede Amaral Lucena, Camilla Rodrigues Seixas, Daniel Fernandes Teodoro, Danillo Alfredo Rios Junior, Danilo Fauster de Souza, Débora Meyer Rosa, Elvis Eli Martins Filho, Felipe Cardoso do Nascimento, Fernanda Nascimento Oliveira, Gabriel Pilon Galvani, Giovana de Castro Vaz, Guilherme Cardoso Ricardo Martins, Gustavo Costa Vieira Novaes, Ingrid Sthéfane Santos Andrade, Isabela Pimenta Gravina, Ivo Ribeiro de Carvalho, Jhoseyr Davison Voos dos Santos, João Lucas Moraes Pereira, Kalline

Arnoldo Oscar Anniehs, pastor and evangelist, was born February 26, 1915, in the city of Curitiba, in the state of Parana, Brazil.¹ Arnoldo was one of the six children of Alberto Anniehs (1888-1980)² and Martha Seeling Anniehs³ (1889-1982). His parents were Seventh-day Adventists.⁴ He spent his childhood in the city of Campinas, state of Sao Paulo. He completed elementary school in the city of Curitiba⁵ in 1928⁶ and continued his studies at Brazil College, where he completed his admission course in 1932.⁷ Around 1938 he was invited to be the first agricultural administrator of the Petrópolis Adventist Academy, located in the city of Petrópolis, state of Rio de Janeiro. Arnoldo was also the first student to come to the institution⁸ and he stayed there until 1940.⁹ The following year he went back to the Colégio Adventista Brasileiro where he completed his studies in theology in 1944.¹⁰ On December 28, 1944, he married Sarah Waldvogel Maluf (1918-2004), who was a teacher in Adventist schools,¹¹ and from that union were born Arnoldo, Valter, and Marisa.¹²

In 1945 Anniehs became a teacher of religious education at Educandário Adventista de Butiá in the city of Curitiba and an evangelist for the Parana-Santa Catarina Conference.¹³ That same year he and his wife engaged in the evangelization of an indigenous group from the Taquara de Baixo region in the state of Parana.¹⁴ In 1946 he returned as director of the farm and a teacher at the Petrópolis Adventist Academy until 1947.¹⁵ Next he became director of the Publishing Department of the Bahia-Sergipe Mission.¹⁶ In 1951 he became an evangelist and pastor for the Espírito Santo Conference,¹⁷ working among German families from the Serra Pelada region, state of Espírito Santo. In 1952 he assisted Pastor Walter Schubert, evangelist of the South American Division. From this experience he developed an even greater appreciation for the work of an evangelist.¹⁸ He conducted evangelistic meetings in the cities of Aimorés (1953)¹⁹ and Afonso Cláudio. He then took over the district of the city of Vitória, the capital of Espírito Santo.²⁰ He was ordained to the ministry in 1956.²¹

He stayed in the Espírito Santo Conference until 1959 when he was appointed evangelist in the São Paulo Conference.²² During this time he conducted evangelistic meetings in several cities in the state of São Paulo, such as Presidente Venceslau (1959),²³ Pacaembu (1960),²⁴ Registro (1961),²⁵ Araras (1962),²⁶ Leme (1962),²⁷ Moji Mirim (1963),²⁸ Cruzeiro (1969)²⁹ and 1970³⁰), Araraquara (1971),³¹ and Taboão da Serra (1978).³² Arnoldo worked actively in the conference for 21 years, retiring in 1980.³³

Following his retirement, Arnoldo remained in the state of São Paulo. He lived in the area surrounding Brazil College and in the cities of Itatiba, Araras, and Artur Nogueira. In these places he continued to preach the gospel, participating in missionary activities of the local churches and giving Bible studies until one month before his death³⁴ on March 22, 1993³⁵ in the city of Artur Nogueira,³⁶ where he was buried.³⁷

SOURCES

“A TV Como Instrumento Para a Pregação.” *Revista Adventista*, year 76, no. 11, November 1981, 6. Accessed November 17, 2016, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

“Alberto Anniehs,” *Revista Adventista*, year 76, no. 3, March 1981, 37. Accessed November 17, 2016, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

“Arnoldo Oscar Anniehs.” National Center of Adventist History (Online), September 24, 2013.

Autobiographical Information of Arnoldo Oscar Anniehs. In: Collection of the National Center of Adventist History/Ellen G. White Research Center: UNASP-EC. Shelf 2. Rack 13. Folder/Box “Anniehs, Arnoldo Oscar.” Accessed November 17, 2016.

Bezerra, Severino. “Notas do Evangelismo – Paulista Leste.” *Revista Adventista*, year 73, June 1978, 18. Accessed on February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

Campolongo, A. “Prefeito Entrega Certificados da Voz da Profecia.” *Revista Adventista*, year 59, no. 10, October 1964, 29. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

Félix, Osvaldo. “Notas e Notícias Paulistas – Evangelismo.” *Revista Adventista*, year 65, no. 3, March 1970, 30. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

Félix, Osvaldo. “Notas e Notícias Paulistas – Temperança.” *Revista Adventista*, year 64, no. 7, July 1969, 31. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

Ferrari, Roberto. “Trinta e Três Ressuscitados em Presidente Venceslau.” *Revista Adventista*, year 55, no. 8, August 1960, 30. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

- Hardt, J.D. "O Instituto Educacional e Agrícola de Petrópolis." *Revista Adventista*, vol. 34, no. 9, September 1939, 10-11. Accessed February 14, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Hosokawa, Kiyoshi "Registro em Marcha." *Revista Adventista*, year 57, no. 1, January 1962, 27. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Hosokawa, Kiyoshi. "Através de um Sonho." *Revista Adventista*, year 59, no. 8, August 1964, 24-25. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Lambeth, C.E. "A Pedra Fundamental do I.E.A.P." *Revista Adventista*, v. 34, no. 8, August 1939, 5. Accessed February 14, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Memorandum sent to the Research Center of UNASP-EC by the Central Brazil Union Conference. In: Collection of the National Center of Adventist History/Ellen G. White Research Center: UNASP-EC. Shelf 2. Rack 13. Folder/Box "Anniehs, Arnaldo Oscar." Accessed November 17, 2016.
- Otto, Alfredo. "Batismo no Interior do Paraná." *Revista Adventista*, year 40, no. 4, April 1945, 29-30. Accessed November 21, 2016, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- "Pastor Arnaldo Anniehs." *Revista Adventista*, year 89, no. 10, October 1993, 39. Accessed November 17, 2016, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Pinto, Reynaldo F.. "Em Araras." *Revista Adventista*, year 57, no. 10, October 1962, 27-28. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Roth, E. "Inauguração do Templo em Aimorés." *Revista Adventista*, year 48, no. 2, February 1953, 13. Accessed February 14, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook*. Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1946. Accessed November 17, 2016, http://docs.adventistarchives.org/docs/YB/YB1946__B.pdf#view=fit
- Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook*. Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1949, 1956-1957. Accessed November 18, 2016, http://docs.adventistarchives.org/docs/YB/YB1949__B.pdf#view=fit
- Silva, Geraldo. "Notícias de Pacaembu." *Revista Adventista*, year 62, no. 3, March 1967, 21-22. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Stabenow, Zeferino. "1978 - Ano Mundial da Educação Adventista: maravilhosa história de um colégio." *Revista Adventista*, year 73, no. 4, May 1978, 14. Accessed February 14, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- Stoehr, Henrique G. "Que Pensas do Teu Futuro?" *Revista Adventista*, v. 35, no. 1, January 1940, 12. Accessed February 14, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.
- "União Sul." *Revista Adventista*, year 66, no. 2, February 1971, 29. Accessed February 15, 2017, <http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/>.

NOTES

1. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs, (Collection of the National Center of Adventist History/Ellen G. White Research Center: UNASP-EC, also known as New Adventist Brazil College, Engenheiro Coelho, SP).?
2. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?
3. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
4. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?
5. Ibid. Also, Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
- 6.
7. Ibid.?
8. Zeferino Stabenow, "1978 - Ano Mundial da Educação Adventista: maravilhosa história de um colégio," *Revista Adventista*, year 73, no. 5, May 1978, 14; and Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?
9. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
10. Ibid.?
11. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?

12. Ibid.?
13. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs; "Butia Academy," *Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook* (Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1946), 230.?
14. Alfredo Otto, "Batismo no Interior do Paraná," *Revista Adventista*, year 40, no. 4, April 1945, 29-30.?
15. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
16. "Bahia and Sergipe Mission," *Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook* (Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1949), 159.?
17. Ibid.?
18. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017; Nigri, Moisés, "1ª Convenção das Lanças Adventistas," *Revista Adventista*, year 47, no. 11, November 1952, 13.?
19. E. Roth, "Inauguração do Templo em Aimorés," *Revista Adventista*, year 48, no. 2, February 1953, 13.?
20. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?
21. "Espírito Santo Conference," *Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook* (Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1956), 143; "Espírito Santo Conference," *Seventh-day Adventist Yearbook* (Washington, D.C.: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1957), 144.?
22. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
23. Roberto Ferrari, "Trinta e Três Ressuscitados em Presidente Venceslau," *Revista Adventista*, year 55, no. 8, August 1960, 30.?
24. Geraldo Silva, "Notícias de Pacaembu," *Revista Adventista*, year 62, March, no. 3, March 1967, 21-22.?
25. Kiyoshi Hosokawa, "Registro em Marcha," *Revista Adventista*, year 57, no. 1, January 1962, 27.?
26. Reynaldo F Pinto., "Em Araras," *Revista Adventista*, year 57, no. 10, October 1962, 27-28.?
27. Kiyoshi Hosokawa, "Através de um Sonho," *Revista Adventista*, year 59, no. 8, August 1964, 24-25.?
28. Campolongo, A., "Prefeito Entrega Certificados da Voz da Profecia," *Revista Adventista*, year 59, no. 10, October 1964, 29.?
29. Osvaldo Félix, "Notas e Notícias Paulistas – Temperança," *Revista Adventista*, year 64, no. 7, July 1969, 31.?
30. Ibid., 30.?
31. "União Sul," *Revista Adventista*, year 66, no. 2, February 1971, 29.?
32. Severino Bezerra, "Notas do Evangelismo – Paulista Leste," *Revista Adventista*, year 73, no. 6, June 1978, 18.?
33. Autobiographical Information of Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs.?
34. Marisa Blahovich, email message to Maria Júlia A. P. dos Santos, February 23, 2017.?
35. Memorandum sent to the Research Center of UNASP-EC by the Central Brazil Union Conference. (Collection of the National Center of Adventist History/Ellen G. White Research Center: UNASP-EC).?
36. "Arnaldo Oscar Anniehs," National Center of Adventist Memory, September 24, 2013, accessed November 17, 2016, http://www.memoriaadventista.com.br/wikiasd/index.php?title=Arnaldo_Oscar_Anniehs.?
37. "Pastor Arnaldo Anniehs," *Revista Adventista*, year 89, no. 10, October 1993, 39.?